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Upgrade of the MINT^{gruen} - Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (SEFI 2017)

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ABSTRACT

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INTRODUCTION

Since 2012, the Technische Universität Berlin offers a special orientation program in the subjects of mathematics, informatics, science and technologies (MINT^{gruen}; English: STEM^{green2}). It is a one year program, which is designed to help high school graduates to find the right study course and prepare them for their later studys. Students can choose between regular MINT subjects and specially developed MINT^{gruen} laboratories. After two semesters the students can decide, which study course they want to continue with and the credit points of the completed subjects, which fit into the chosen study course, are taken into account.

The department of Fluid System Dynamics at the TU Berlin contributes to the orientation of young students by offering a laboratory dealing with fluid mechanics in applied mechanical engineering. The Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (FMPL) provides

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² STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics

fundamental engineering skills by teaching the students all the basics of using engineering software (such as Excel, SolidWorks, VBA) and guides them through advanced usage. It also imparts structured working methods while teaching the importance of sustainable engineering. Students achieve basic and advanced engineering skills (software and working methods) as well as exploring the multifaceted nature and the importance of sustainable engineering at the example of fluid flow machines. The whole laboratory is wrapped in the teaching concept of problem based and project based learning. Since launching the project, it has been continuously evaluated by the students. The results show a very good rating for the teaching approach and a first analysis reveals that more than half of the students participating in the orientation program choose a MINT topic for their later studies.

1 OVERVIEW OF MINT^{GRUEN} (ENGLISH: STEM^{GREEN})

1.1 Structure, numbers and trends

After graduating from high school, young people have to decide what they want to do professionally. Some choose to take an apprenticeship for about 3 years, whereas others choose an academic career. The German universities offer a wide range of possible study courses. Most pupils feel overwhelmed by the countless possibilities and are unsure which course to take. They are expected to decide on “the right” study course which they will be practicing for the rest of their lives. This causes a lot of pressure and makes the decision even harder. Young people feel the need to be guided and orientated. Therefore, the Technische Universität Berlin launched the orientation program in 2012 MINT^{gruen} to show graduated pupils the variety in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics. Since initiating the orientation program, the numbers of participants are steadily rising (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Numbers and trends of the MINT^{gruen} orientation program

Fig. 2 displays the contents and structure of the orientation program, which lasts two semesters. The “Scientific Window” and the “Study Program Decision” are obligate courses, where students gain all necessary information on how to orientate themselves. In the “Scientific Window” the students have to deal with current research topics in the MINT sector and discuss these in terms of sustainability and sustainable development. They share and reflect their experiences in a separated orientation course. This helps the students to get a good impression of the different fields and makes the decision easier. The other modules are facultative and consist of basic lectures (i.e. engineering mathematics) and so-called Project Laboratories, which are explained in the next section. After taking the two-semester program, most of the courses can be transferred to the student’s chosen course of study.

Fig. 2: Structure of the orientation program MINT^{gruen}

1.2 Project Laboratories

One characteristic feature of the orientation program MINT^{gruen} are the above-mentioned Project Laboratories that are specifically designed for MINT^{gruen} students. Especially in the earlier stages of study courses subjects are more theoretical. For a successful orientation, it is mandatory that students discover their practical and project related potentials. Furthermore, the students have to work on projects in their future jobs too and this is a first good practice, which usually appears not until the fourth bachelor semester. Therefore, the orientation program offers a wide variety of laboratories, which cover the following fields (for further information see the following source mentioned in brackets):

- Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory ([1] and this paper)
- Industry-linked Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory
- Mathematical Lab – Mathesis ([5])
- Creativity and Construction ([6])
- Chemistry Project Laboratory ([7], [8])
- Gender in MINT fields ([9])
- Robotic Laboratory
- Vibration Technology Laboratory
- Artefacts in technology and science history
- Environmental Laboratory

The department of Fluid System Dynamic at the TU Berlin contributes to the orientation of young students by offering a laboratory dealing with fluid mechanics in applied mechanical engineering, the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory.

2 STRUCTURE OF THE FLUID MECHANICS PROJECT LABORATORY

Since the FMPL is described in the SEFI 2017 proceedings [1] in detail, only a short recapitulation is given now.

For the students the main goal of the project laboratory is to design a rotor blade for a wind turbine model in small groups of 3 to 5. They design the blade from sketch, over calculations in MS Excel and a CAD³ software, to an actual 3D printed part, and measure it in a wind tunnel. A final report on the students' project is required as well as a final presentation. The report aims at improving the scientific writing skills the presentation is supposed to train the appearance and the speaking in front of an audience. The laboratory's structure is similar to an actual industrial project. Fig. 3 displays the 3D model of the wind turbine in CAD (a) and in reality (b). Fig. 4 illustrates the wind tunnel where the measurements of the rotor blades take place.

³ CAD - computer aided design; possibility to design 3D models of component, part or assembly

Fig. 3: Example of a rotor for a wind turbine model designed by the students

Fig. 4: Wind tunnel used for the rotor measurements

2.1 What's new?

It is an educational and societal task to sharpen the awareness of power producing and power consuming machines. It is pointless if the producers are “clean and green”, while the consumers stay “bad and red”. There is a need of a sustainable and environmentally friendly design for these power consuming fluid flow machines and their hydraulic systems. Consequently, the interest of young students for this topic needs to be awoken.

Power producers (e.g. wind energy, solar power, hydro power) are getting a lot of attention from the media while power consumers (e.g. industrial pumps, washing machines, dryers and many more) are left behind. Since it is easier to attract young students with power producing turbines, a new water turbine concept is added to the pre-existing wind turbine concept to upgrade the fluid mechanics project laboratory. Fig. 5 pictures the new test stand as a 3D model. Once students are attracted to a topic they were interested in beforehand, it is easier to cover uncommon topics like wastewater pumps parenthetically to build awareness and arouse interest. Furthermore, it is easier to implement a second turbine into the pre-existing concept because their design guidelines provide similarities.

Fig. 5: Water turbine test stand and 3D printed rotor model

Since the water turbine concept had to be integrated in the pre-existing wind turbine concept, the structure of the project laboratory remains nearly the same. Students can now choose between *wind* and *water* and are put into two separate groups, which meet on different days of the week. Fig. 6 summarises the FMPL's structure and which topics are discussed at a certain point.

Phase	Duration	Contents	Achieved skills
1	2 weeks	Organisation and project management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of group projects Time management Creating project schedules with MS Excel
2	3 weeks	Fluid mechanics, wind energy and hydro power	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic calculations in MS Excel Handcrafting and testing air- and hydrofoils Advanced usage of MS Excel (links, functions, variables) Complete rotor calculation
3	2 weeks	Computer aided design (CAD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction into 3D modeling Basic usage of CAD software Advanced usage of CAD tools (scripts & macros) Manufacturing of the student's rotor
4	3 weeks	Measurement techniques and test stands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purpose of test stands Usage of sensors Measurement of each group's rotor Advanced usage of MS Excel (graphs, functions)
5	3 weeks	Writing and presenting skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating templates for MS Word Basic usage of MS PowerPoint Scientific writing recommendations

Fig. 6: Structure of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory

There is one main advantage in adding a second turbine into the pre-existing concept. To expand on these advantages, the next chapter introduces the teaching technique of problem based and project based learning. Furthermore it will be explained how the expansion supports the students in their development.

2.2 Project based and problem based learning

Project based and problem based learning is well summarized in the following two citations:

*Besides many facts, problem based learning teaches the ability to develop strategies to solve a problem.*⁴

*Learning as a problem based process is executed in a specific, scope related context. Trainees learn from an example and are able to transfer their knowledge to a new similar problem or situation.*⁵

By nature, a project laboratory includes problem based and project based learning methods, since the students face a pre-designed problem that has to be solved on their own. To use the problem based and project based teaching method to its full potential, it is expanded to satisfy student's needs:

A German survey from 2015 analyses current study states and student's orientation success. This survey [3, pp. 21-30] shows that students wish for a better support regarding the achievement of engineering skills (which were not taught in school) and handling of common engineering software such as MS Excel. A majority of the students mentioned a knowledge gap between the schools' content of teaching and required engineering skills at the university. Finally yet importantly, students criticise the lack of support for achieving scientific writing skills regarding their homework and their bachelor theses. The goal of the laboratory is to satisfy those needs and show the multi-facetted world of fluid flow machines.

In order to satisfy those needs while reaching the main goal of the project laboratory (the design of a rotor blade), the problem based and project based teaching method is used as shown in *Fig. 7*. Like a real industrial project, the laboratory is split in four main phases (project scheduling, calculation and design, measurements, documentation), which are each divided into at least two sub-phases and corresponding problems to solve (not pictured in *Fig. 7*). These sub-problems are similar in the way they can be solved. The solution of the first problem is approached from a certain angle, while the solution of the second (or further) problem(s) is (are) developed from a different angle. But the main structure for solving the task remains the same: a short theoretical input, followed by a practical phase, leading to a final result (cycle in *Fig. 7*). While doing so, different engineering skills, as mentioned in the survey [3], are taught.

Fig. 7: Concept of problem based and project based learning at the FMPL

⁴Analogously translated from [9] p. 3; Similar definitions in English can be found in [11]

⁵Analogously translated from [10] p.18; Similar definitions in English can be found in [11]

After introducing the concept of problem based learning and how it is utilized in the fluid mechanics project laboratory, the main advantage of integrating another turbine into the existing concept gets sharper: As mentioned, the students are split into a *water* and a *wind* group. Before the students solve the main task for their own turbine, an example of the respectively other turbine is used to impart knowledge by the teacher. Subsequently, it gets easier for the students to adapt to their own problem and find a solution on their own. Furthermore, the discussed topics, wind and water turbine, are put into relation with each other. After applying their knowledge two times in a power producer related case, a power consumer case is investigated. This strategy leads to the above-mentioned interest in power producers and consumers, which is also one goal of the fluid mechanics project laboratory.

Another aim is to encourage the students to work independently by providing as many free choices as possible, fitting to the student's current level. That is one reason why the project was expanded with a second selectable turbine. The students now have the option to choose either work on the wind turbine model or on a water turbine model. Furthermore, the expansion of the project shows the great variety in the field of engineering in terms of renewable energy. The students also get to see the difficulties that are posed by conducting measurements in water.

Summary:

- The students gain knowledge about power producers and consumers at the same time, while understanding the importance of a sustainable und environmentally friendly design of both categories.
- The students are, due to the teaching concept, able to describe a problem and find a solution similar to a problem solved before.
- The student's wishes, as shown in the above-mentioned survey [3], are fulfilled.
- The students are getting encouraged to work independently, since they can decide on their own as much as possible.

3 RESULTS AND TEACHING APPROACH

Analysis reveal that more than half of the students participating in the orientation program in 2017 choose a MINT topic for their later studies (*Fig. 8*).

Fig. 8: Number of students considering a MINT related study course at TU Berlin

Even people, who leave the university and start an apprenticeship, consider the contents of the FMPL as useful for their later jobs. The Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory as a whole was rated in 2017 with “very good” (Fig. 9) and with “good” in 2018 (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9: Student's summarised rating of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory 2017

Fig. 10: Student's summarised rating of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory 2018

When comparing Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, a drop in the overall rating of 0.4 points is noticeable. It is assumed that this drop is caused due to a personnel change mid semester and is not related to the implementation of the second turbine. Future data will tell if this assumption is correct.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Whilst lectures mostly use frontal teaching methods, the Project Laboratories focus on practical tasks and give the students the possibility to create a MINT-related object on their own. The teaching concept of this Fluid Dynamics Project Laboratory contributes highly to the orientation of our students. A huge field of fluid mechanical engineering is covered. Students gain a diversified insight on fluid mechanic related topics and their field of appliance. Due to the practical concept of the laboratory, students achieve various engineering skills and working methods, which can be used in many study courses, apprenticeships or even in their later jobs. Due to the teaching of basic and advanced skills regarding engineering software (MS Excel, MS Word, MS PowerPoint, SolidWorks), students are well prepared for their course of study. In this program, the students get supported in general studying related aspects as well as fluid mechanic related topics.

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